

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF METHODS AND APPROACHES FOR EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT: This paper is aimed at describing different types of methods and approaches in an English classroom. The writer investigates them according to the latest experiments held by the linguists to observe the effectiveness of historical and modern ones. The data showed in this paper may differ from each other as each linguist received not the same outcome and conclusion in that or this method, but they all can advise which to use according to the aim of teaching.

There were three steps used in this research, i.e., collecting data, analyzing data, and presenting the result of data analysis. Firstly, the data were collected by using observation method with tapping, nonparticipant-observatory, sorting, and note taking. Secondly, the data were analyzed by using referential identity method and translation method with comparing, equalizing technique, and differentiating technique. Finally, the result of analysis is illustrated by using formal and informal method.

KEYWORDS: method, approach, direct method, communicative language teaching, language, students, communicative skills.

Целью данной статьи является описание различных типов методов и подходов на уроках английского языка. Писатель исследует их на основе новейших экспериментов, проведенных лингвистами по наблюдению за эффективностью исторических и современных. Данные, представленные в этой статье, могут отличаться друг от друга, поскольку каждый лингвист получил не одинаковый результат и заключение по тому или иному методу, но все они могут посоветовать, какой использовать в соответствии с целью обучения.

В этом исследовании использовались три этапа: сбор данных, анализ данных и

представление результатов анализа данных. Во-первых, данные были собраны с помощью наблюдения.

метод с прослушиванием, сортировкой и ведением заметок.

Во-вторых, данные были проанализированы с использованием метода референтной идентичности и метода перевода со сравнением, уравниванием и дифференцированием.

Наконец, результат анализа иллюстрируется с использованием формального и неформального метода.

Ключевые слова: метод, подход, прямой метод, коммуникативное обучение языку, язык, учащиеся, коммуникативные навыки.

ANNOTATSIIYA: Ushbu maqola ingliz tili darolarida qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan turli xil metod va yondashuvlarni tavsiflashga qaratilgan. Muallif ularni tilshunoslar tomonidan o'tkazilgan tajribalarda tarixiy va zamonaviy metod va yondashuvlarning nechog'lik samarali ekanligiga ko'ra tekshiradi. Ushbu maqolada ko'rsatilgan ma'lumotlar bir-biridan farq qilishi mumkin, chunki har bir tilshunos u yoki bu metodda turli xil natija va xulosaga ega bo'lishgan, ammo ularning barchasi o'qitish maqsadiga ko'ra qaysi biri afzal ekanligini maslahat bera oladi.

Ushbu tadqiqot uch bosqichda amalga oshirilgan, ya'ni ma'lumotlarni to'plash, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va ma'lumotlar tahlili natijalarini taqdim etish. Avvalo, ma'lumotlar kuzatish, saralash va qayd qilish orqali yig'ilgan. So'ngra, ma'lumotlar afzalliligiga ko'ra taqqoslash, tenglashtirish va farqlash texnikasi yordamida tahlil qilindi. Nihoyat, tahlil natijasi rasmiy va norasmiy usullardan foydalangan holda yoritilgan.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: metod, yondashuv, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri metod, kommunikativ til o'qitish, til, talabalarlar, kommunikativ qobiliyatlar.

INTRODUCTION

"An international language belongs to its users, not to the countries whose national languages have become internationalized" (Edge 1993). In our world today, English became one of the widely used languages in different spheres of life, both in educational and non- educational fields. According to some statistics, English is being spoken by two billion people worldwide, with native speakers making up about 400 millions of them because of the reason English became lingua franca for business, diplomacy and travel. As it occupies an equal central position in fields of academia and research, a number of researches are being done to investigate new ways of teaching in appropriate ways which are suitable in 21st century, while a number of researchers are trying to reveal new features of approaches and methods from 1900s. In this article we will review some examples of current methods and approach in teaching English .

LITERATURE AND METHODS

Obviously, great number of linguists and methodologists are observing and analysing the techniques, approaches and methods according to different criteria, as some of them try to renew historical ones while others create new. Among all methodology investigators Richards and Rodgers, M. Betti, C.Mukalel, Nagaraj and others made a noticeable impact. They all investigated historical and current approaches as well as techniques, analyzed deeply and sorted according to the aim of instruction and so on.

In Uzbekistan, J. Jalolov, G. Tajibayev, A.Haydarov, Shabonov and To'xtamirzayev did investigations on language teaching. On the same time giving their own reviews to methods, they used the latest data by well known linguists worldwide.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Jack C. Richards and Theodore S. Rodgers (2014) implemented a noticeable impact on the necessity of methods and approaches in English learning process. They discussed about the methods that have attracted support at different times and in places during the last 30 years, but not being accepted now. According to the consideration, while Total Physical Response, The Silent way, and Suggestopedia are no longer widely used, the Direct Method, Audiolingualism, the Situational Approach were adopted almost universally and achieved the status of methodological orthodoxy. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) marks the beginning of a major paradigm shift within language teaching in the twentieth century, one whose ramifications continue to be felt today. The general principles of CLT are still widely accepted in language teaching today these principles have been open to various interpretations, and those favoring the approach may weigh the value of fluency and accuracy in different ways. Aspects of CLT may also be used to support other approaches and methods. Content-Based Instruction (CBI) can be regarded as a logical development of some of the core principles of CLT, particularly those that relate to the role of meaning in language learning. Because CBI provides an approach that is particularly suited to prepare ESL students to enter elementary, secondary, or tertiary education, it is widely used in English-speaking countries around the world, particularly in the United States. CLIL, a related approach, has become popular in Europe; both approaches involve a merging of content and language (Richards and Rodgers, 2014: 81). They pointed out that very large number of textbooks are based on Oral Approach as it has been long lasting and it has shaped the design of many EFL textbooks and courses for students. Framework

for National curricula in English as well as other subjects in some countries is hold by Competency- based Instruction.

According to Philipp Kamhuber, the Communicative Approach and Task-Based Language Teaching are the ones to investigate the role and effectiveness in teaching grammar for ELT textbooks. He did not only explore their role in teaching grammar, but the comparison Austrian and Spanish ELT textbooks is concerned the attention, as well. The Grammar-Translation Method, the Direct Method, Audiolingualism, the Natural Approach and Communicative Language Teaching including Task-Based Learning are considered relevant for the development of grammar teaching by the author.

Another linguist Mohammed Jasim Betti tries to familiarize the Iraqi teacher of English with key aspects of methodology and suggests strategies and techniques through which the elements and communicative skills of the language can be taught. He pays special attention to the conditions and factors influencing the effectiveness of the teaching of the language in school in his book “ Approaches and methods of teaching English as a foreign language”. Hence the book is intended for teaching English as a Foreign language, it includes different ideas on using strategies and approaches substance and techniques for. Teaching sounds, grammar,vocabulary and cultural subsystems. Suggestions for developing the communication skills; listening, speaking, reading and writing are also included. As the linguist aimed to broaden the instruction about the peculiarities and features of language teaching and learning process, the book’s first two chapters are dedicted to basic principles, techniques , methods and approaches in teaching.

As he points “Indirect and the Direct methods , are rather extreme. On the one hand, the chief purpose of the grammar-translation method is to develop an ability to translate while the spoken language is neglected. The Direct method on the other hand lays heavy emphasis on the oral aspects of the language and intensive speech practice. Yet it discards the use of translation” . Unlike the Audio- Lingual Method, the Communicative Approach gives priority to the semantic content of language learning. That is pupils learn the grammatical form through meanng, and not the other way round. Though this new strategy helps the learners apply what they have learnt of the linguistic knowledge, without any difficulty, to real life situations involving interactive processes, it relies on the functional- Notional syllabus which places great demands on the pupils and a few categories of language functions are not systematically graded that brings some confusion and makes challenges on

teaching the functions appropriately. He showed the Eclectic Approach as a framework for techniques and procedures drawn from various methods and it is useful in practical situations in the classroom.

The differences between Translation Methods and the Direct Method have earned a special attention on the manual by Shabanov and To'xtamirzaev. They considered that all the types of the Translation Method are under the goal of understanding the meaning during the translation, on the other hand no L1 is useable in Direct method. The learners should associate the connection between the word and subject following understanding and thinking in L2. As the goal of Direct method is learning the language in a practical point of view, rather than theory, the Audio-lingual and the Audio-visual methods are separated as a modern version of the Direct Method (Shabanov and To'xtamirzaev, 2009). They showed a basic disadvantage of the Audio-lingual Method to pursue in primary education system in Uzbekistan. As the speech examples can be produced without the role of mental process that will not be illustrated any rules, leads the lack of scientific frame, it can be concluded as an inappropriate illustration of methodology.

CONCLUSION

As English became global language, as more and more different cultures are using it, there is the necessity of empowering it with renewing and creating new way of teaching that will be ideal for the purpose of learners. Above mentioned linguists had a noticeable impact on English teaching with their precious analysis, facts and recommendations

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